

**THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED
AND RUBBER TOUGHENED POLYPROPYLENE**

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ABSTRACT

The microstructure and mechanical properties of injection moulded polypropylene with various proportions of glass fibre and rubber have been studied. The microstructure was investigated extensively using image analysis techniques to determine the fibre length distribution, fibre orientation distribution and rubber particle size and distribution. The fibre/matrix interfacial shear strength has been estimated by a modified fragmentation test. The tensile properties of the composite grades have been modelled on the basis of the structure and good agreement obtained with experiment. Linear elastic and elastic-plastic fracture mechanics tests revealed distinctly different behaviour under different test conditions. This is consistent with an observed change in fracture morphology.

KEY WORDS: Short Fibre Composite; Microstructure; Mechanical Modelling; Fracture Mechanics; Interface.

1. INTRODUCTION

Short glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics (SFRTTP's) are used in a wide range of low-cost high-volume applications. Although they have lower specific mechanical properties than continuous-fibre reinforced composites, SFRTTP's are attractive on account of their low-cost enhanced properties and because they can be moulded into complex shapes at high production rates.

The general effect of short glass-fibre additions to the polymer is to raise the elastic modulus and strength whilst reducing ductility. Toughness is also influenced, but it is more difficult to characterise because it is affected by stress concentrations, test piece geometry, microstructural morphology, strain rate and environmental conditions.

This work is centred on a polypropylene base polymer, to which glass fibre, a polyolefin rubber and a coupling agent were added. The coupling agent is designed to promote adhesion of the polymer matrix to the glass fibre surface. Grades containing different fractions of the constituents were produced and then injection moulded into test pieces of varying shapes, sizes and geometry. The aims of the work were to investigate and to model the basic mechanical properties through a determination of the microstructure and

fibre/matrix interfacial properties. An investigation of the fracture mechanics and toughening modes was also carried out.

2. MATERIALS AND SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The base polymer was a polypropylene homopolymer powder. Polyolefin rubber granules were introduced at levels between zero and 40% by weight of the base polymer. A commercially available E-glass was added to produce nominal fibre fractions of 0, 15, 30 and 40% by weight of the final compound. A coupling agent was also incorporated to promote greater adhesion between the polymer and the fibre.

Compounds were produced in a twin screw extruder and the resulting granules were injection moulded into a variety of test pieces. As far as practicable, the moulding conditions were kept constant in order to minimize possible microstructural differences.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 Tensile Testing Tensile testing was performed at room temperature using an Instron 1195 testing machine at a cross head speed of 50mm/min. All tensile mechanical property tests were carried out on the injection moulded dog-bone tensile test pieces.

3.2 Microstructural Characterisation Short fibre reinforced thermoplastics contain a range of fibre lengths which are distributed in a three dimensional manner throughout the specimen. The rubber particles are resident within the polymer as a separate phase. Quantifying the glass fibre and rubber particles size and dispersion is essential for accurate mechanical modelling.

3.2.1 Fibre Length Distributions The matrix from representative mouldings was burned off to leave only glass fibres. The fibres were observed under an optical microscope and the image fed to an image analyser. The analyser edited crossed and touching fibres digitally before they were measured and counted. A large number of fibres from many different fields need to be counted to produce an accurate characterisation of the length distribution. A total count of circa 7000 fibres appeared to produce a representative distribution of fibre lengths.

Errors in the fibre count were incurred by the image analyser. The large range of fibre lengths i.e. 10-2500 μ m, imposed limitations upon the screen sizes and magnification of the analyser. As fibre length increases the probability that a fibre is lying with part of its length outside the field of view increases. Such fibres would be measured as being shorter than their actual length. Over a total distribution this had the effect of reducing the count of long fibres and increasing the count of shorter fibres. These errors can be corrected by use of a computer simulation of the process by which the fibre lengths are measured and hence determining a correction procedure for lengths recorded correctly.

3.2.2 Fibre Orientation Distributions Fibre orientation distributions were measured quantitatively in a similar manner to the fibre length distributions. However, for fibre orientation distributions the fibres were observed whilst still embedded in the matrix. The image analyser measured the

orientation of the fibres with respect to the mould fill direction. Measurements were recorded at known distances across the breadth of the section. Sections were taken at multiple distances through the moulded samples thickness and breadth to enable an overall picture of the fibre orientation through the whole sample.

3.2.3 Rubber Particle Dispersion Small specimens were sliced in a cryogenic microtome at -100°C . This produces a flat face on the donor sample from which the rubber could be dissolved and the resultant holes observed using scanning electron microscopy. The rubber was dissolved from the freshly prepared surface by suspending the specimen above boiling heptane for 60 seconds. This method dissolves the rubber but does not affect the polypropylene. The specimens were then sputter coated with gold and observed by SEM.

3.2.4 Interfacial Shear Stress Thin sheets of polypropylene were compression moulded. Two sheets were sandwiched around a single glass fibre and bonded together under heat and pressure. The specimen was loaded on a straining stage of a microscope and the lengths of the resultant fibre fragments were measured.

Kelly and Tyson¹ have related the critical length, l_c , to the interfacial shear strength, τ , through a force balance around the embedded fibre. The resulting expression for l_c is

$$l_c = (\sigma \cdot d) / (2 \cdot \tau) \tag{3.1}$$

where σ is the ultimate tensile strength of the fibre and d is the diameter of the fibre. A normal distribution of fragment lengths should be obtained ranging between $\frac{1}{2}l_c$ to l_c . Accordingly the peak of the histogram corresponds to $\frac{3}{4}l_c$. Normally the fragment length distribution is broader than the 2:1 ratio predicted. This is due to flaws in the fibre which cause its strength to depend on length. The peak of the broadened histogram should still correspond to $\frac{3}{4}l_c$.

Figure 1 Typical fibre length distributions

4. COMPOSITE MICROSTRUCTURE

4.1 Fibre Length Distributions Figure 1 (as above) shows corrected log-normal distributions for the three fibre filled grades. As the volume fraction of fibres was increased the level of attrition during extrusion increased due to a greater probability of fibre-fibre interactions. This results in a general reduction in the average fibre length of the final moulded specimens. The maximum fibre length was reduced as was the total fraction of long fibres. The proportion of short fibres was increased and the peak of the curve moved towards the shorter fibres.

4.2 Fibre Orientation Distributions

The skin/core structure of typical SF RTP's requires many slices to be analysed to produce an accurate representation. Figure 2 shows the orientation distribution across the core, through the 12mm breadth of a tensile specimen. The asymmetry was due to side gating of the specimen. Figure 3 shows the distribution through the 3mm thickness of the same specimen, i.e. perpendicular to that of figure 2. In this plane

Figure 2 Fibre orientation distribution through the core

there were far fewer misoriented fibres. This is due to the close proximity of the mould surfaces constraining the fibres in plane. The wider section represented in figure 2 allowed a greater freedom for rotation of the fibres. Figure 3 shows that the majority of fibres were rotated in only one plane. In this way the composite can be treated as a laminate made up of many plies, or slices.

The orientation distribution can be evaluated for many sections through the specimens thickness. To quantify this the Krenchel² orientation factor, η_o , was used. The term η_o is calculated from a summation of the fibre fraction, a_k , oriented in angular increments away from the applied load, θ_k :

$$\eta_o = \sum a_k \cdot \cos^4 \theta_k \quad (4.1)$$

Figure 3 Fibre orientation distribution perpendicular to core

The Krenchel factor can be calculated for the individual slices and a weighted average obtained for the composite as a whole.

4.3 Rubber Particle Dispersion The rubber particles were observed to be non-spherical in shape. This was caused by shear of the melt during injection moulding. The particles were approximately 2µm in diameter. The size of the particles did not change with increasing volume fraction and were distributed uniformly throughout the composite. There was no segregation to fibre surfaces.

4.4 Interfacial Shear Strength The values obtained for τ were:

Polypropylene homopolymer	10.80 MPa
Polypropylene & coupling	18.20 MPa
Polypropylene & 10% rubber	4.73 MPa
Polypropylene & 10% rubber & coupling	9.67 MPa

The addition of a small quantity of rubber significantly reduced the measured interfacial shear strength; this is probably associated with the reduction in the modulus of the matrix due to the rubber.

4. MECHANICAL MODELLING

Bader and Bowyer³ attempted to account for the degradation of mechanical properties due to fibre damage during injection moulding of reinforced thermoplastics by studying the fibre length distributions in mouldings. They used a mathematical model in which contributions to composite stress/strain behaviour from fibres of sub-critical and super-critical lengths were summed separately over the effective range of lengths. Bader and Bowyer obtained the expression

Figure 4 Experimental and predictive stress/strain curves

$$\sigma_c = \eta(X+Y) + Z \tag{4.2}$$

where

$$X = \Sigma_{(subcritical)} \tau l_i V_i / 2r_f \tag{4.3}$$

$$Y = \Sigma_{(supercritical)} E_f E_c (1 - (E_f E_c r_f / 2l_j \tau)) V_j \tag{4.4}$$

and

$$Z = E_m E_c (1 - V_f) \tag{4.5}$$

where η is an orientation factor; V_i and V_j are the volume subfractions of fibres with lengths l_i and l_j, respectively, E_m is the matrix modulus and V_f the total fibre volume fraction of fibre. In equation (4.3), the summation

extends over all fibre-length intervals below the critical length and in equation (4.4) over all intervals above the critical length.

While applying the equations given above, Bader and Bowyer assumed that the value of the shear stress, τ , is the same at all values of the composite strain, ϵ_c .

Mittal and Gupta⁴ used a similar method but developed a linear relationship between the interfacial shear stress and the composite stress, i.e. $\tau = K\sigma_c$. The principal contribution of the equation $\tau = K\sigma_c$ is a more realistic evaluation of the critical length during the deformation process. The Kelly and Tyson definition of the critical length can now be written as

$$l_c = (E_f r_f \epsilon_c) / K \sigma_c = (E_f r_f / K) \cdot (\epsilon_c / \sigma_c) \quad (4.6)$$

The duplex matrix phase of rubber spheres in continuous polypropylene is treated as a single homogeneous phase using particulate theory.

Through an iterative process the fibre length distributions, Krenchel orientation factor and interfacial shear stress can be applied to the above equations to produce accurate predictive stress/strain curves for a range of composite grades. A series of curves is shown in figure 4.

5. FRACTURE MECHANICS AND FAILURE MECHANISMS

Fracture tests were carried out at high strain rates to investigate impact resistance. Slower rate tests, in which controlled crack propagation occurred, provide fracture toughness data.

Fracture surface morphology was studied in order to gain an understanding of the toughening mechanisms which operate in these materials within different loading regimes.

5.1 Fracture Toughness Measurement

5.1.1 LEFM Impact Testing Instrumented falling weight impact testing (IFWIT) was employed to measure linear elastic fracture mechanics parameters on single edge notched bend specimens (SENB) from a limited number of grades. SENB specimens were cut from the 10mm thick plaques to ensure plane strain conditions predominated. For the fibre filled grades, specimens were cut parallel (denoted 0) and perpendicular (denoted 90) to the melt fill direction. Specimen geometry, notching and crack sharpening were in accordance with the procedure outlined in the European Structural Integrity Society (ESIS) protocol⁵. Testing was performed in 3 point bending at 23°C and at a strain rate of 1 m/s.

5.1.2 LEFM Controlled Crack Growth The basic testing procedure follows that detailed by the ESIS protocol⁵. Compact tension (CT) specimens were machined out of 10mm thick plaques from a 30% glass filled grade and a 30% glass, 30% rubber filled grade. The notch of the specimen lying parallel to the melt fill direction was sharpened with a scalpel blade. In all specimens the crack was propagated parallel to the melt fill direction, and consequently with the predominant orientation of fibres in the skin of the specimen, to ensure that the crack would run perpendicular to the loading direction.

The CT specimen was supported by pins in an Instron loading frame and then placed under tension in order to propagate a pre-initiated crack through the specimen. The load required to propagate the crack was measured together with the displacement of the loading pins. The length of the crack was measured in situ using a metal foil which was bonded to the surface of the specimen and connected to a bridge type amplifier. As the crack propagated through the specimen, it also tore the foil resulting in a change in the electrical resistance of the foil. Accurate measurements can be achieved for up to 30mm of crack growth. This technique has the advantage that K_{IC} and G_{IC} can be calculated for both crack initiation and propagation. Specimens were strained at rates of 1mm/min and 0.17m/s.

5.1.3 Elastic Plastic Fracture Mechanics The ESIS testing protocol⁶ for conducting J integral tests on plastics uses a new technique for measuring the crack advance, da , in the material, and for extrapolating the data to determine J_C .

Single edge notched bend specimens identical to those used in the instrumented falling weight impact test were used for the J integral procedure. The novelty of this technique is that once the crack has been grown, the specimens are cut in half perpendicular to the notch along their length. The vicinity of the crack is ground smooth and coated with a thin layer of silver paint to help distinguish between the actual crack and the plastic zone. The specimens are placed in a hand operated three point bend rig below a video microscope. A small load is applied to open the crack and its length is measured. The J integral analysis is then applied.

5.2 Fracture Toughness Results The results of the fracture toughness testing are listed in the table I.

The CT specimens with the fractometer foil attached indicated that the crack initiated well before peak load, figure 5. K_{IC} and G_{IC} were evaluated at crack initiation (Init') and at peak load where crack lengths were approximately 5 to 10mm beyond the original razor notch. At these crack lengths conditions approximating stable crack growth were achieved. The IFWIT results from SENB test specimens were calculated at peak load only.

The J integral values were extrapolated from a power law fit and produced an elastic-plastic value of fracture toughness at crack initiation.

Figure 5 Crack growth within a CT specimen as a function of load and displacement

Strain Rate	1mm/min			0.17m/s		1m/s	
Fracture Parameter	J_C (kJ/m ²)	K_C (MN/m ^{3/2})					
Crack Length	0.2mm	Init'n	Peak Load	Init'n	Peak Load	Peak Load	
PP	2.10					1.82	
PP & 30% R	2.27					1.97	
PP & 30% G 0	1.41					4.01	
PP & 30% G 90	1.33	2.41	6.04	0.70	2.30	3.09	
PP & G & R 0	1.84					4.02	
PP & G & R 90	1.14	1.96	4.18	0.45	2.75	2.99	
		G_C (kJ/m ²)					Charpy (J)
PP						1.11	0.56
PP & 30% R						2.90	1.55
PP & 30% G 0						6.46	2.28
PP & 30% G 90		3.44	11.7	2.50	11.8	3.63	
PP & G & R 0						8.03	2.96
PP & G & R 90		3.45	9.67	2.80	9.75	5.29	

Table I Fracture Mechanics Results

The addition of rubber to the matrix increases consistently the toughness of the material at impact speeds. Energy absorbing processes occurring during loading of ductile polymers at temperatures at and above that of the T_g of the matrix components are shear flow and craze formation. Such mechanisms would help to account for the increased toughness of these materials. At the lower straining rates the addition of rubber decreases the fracture toughness of fibre filled grades. The reduction in modulus of the matrix caused by the rubber reduces the reinforcing ability of the fibres and their associated pull-out energy. The elastic-plastic fracture mechanics and high strain rate LEFM testing show opposite trends. The elastic-plastic results suggest that the addition of glass fibres to the matrix reduces the energy required to initiate fracture as they act as stress concentrators. At the higher strain rate of the IFWIT this effect is reversed implying that the fibres toughen the material by increasing the energy required to initiate and propagate fracture. When fracture surfaces were observed in SEM, a clear difference in fracture morphology as a function of strain rate could be seen. This manifested itself as a change in the modes of the matrix failure and fibre pull-out. At low strain rates the matrix fracture surface exhibits large shear and plastic deformation. Under impact conditions the fracture surface is planar in nature. There is little or no plastic deformation. Rubber particles are pulled-out of the matrix and can be seen clearly as spheres protruding from the fracture surfaces. Such polymeric materials are viscoelastic solids. Their propensity to anelastic and plastic deformation is reduced when they are tested at high strain rates and/or at low temperatures. The reduced deformability causes a formerly tough polymer to respond in a brittle manner. It is reasonable to suggest that the toughening effect of the rubber in the matrix is greater at low strain rates.

*SEM photomicrographs of fracture surfaces at two strain rates:
1mm/min, 1m/s.*

At low strain rates the surfaces of pulled-out fibres were clean of any additional material. The surfaces of pulled-out fibres at higher strain rates exhibited a sheath of adherent matrix material. Bailey and Bader⁷ observed a similar process with short glass fibre reinforced Nylon and suggested that the cohesive failure of the sheathed fibre absorbed far more energy than the adhesive failure of the unsheathed fibre. At low strain rates the fibres debonded easily from the matrix acting as stress raisers, and this accounts for the J integral results. At higher strain rates the fibres toughened the matrix through the sheathing effect.

The purpose of the compact tension LEFM testing was to investigate this process further at two significantly different strain rates under more controlled conditions. At both strain rates similar trends to the J integral behaviour were produced. The higher strain rate was limited by the cross head speed of a hydraulic load frame. The maximum obtainable speed was 0.17m/s. At this speed the fracture surfaces of the specimens exhibited only slight patchy sheathing of pulled-out fibres. Fibre sheathing is very strain rate dependent. The recorded speeds of the impact tests were the speeds of the impactors on contact with the specimen. The elastic nature of the specimen causes it to deflect upon impact. When the crack finally initiates and begins to propagate the crack speed may be many times greater than the speed of the impactor. The fastest strain rate obtained in the CT test was not sufficient to reproduce the results obtained from impact testing.

In summary, at low strain rates the plastic deformation of the matrix and rubber particles are the predominant forms of toughening. Under such conditions the fibres weaken the system by introducing stress raisers and discontinuities to the matrix. At impact speeds the viscoelastic polymer matrix cannot respond fast enough to the loading conditions and fractures in a brittle manner. However, at such speeds the fibres act to toughen the material by increasing the pull-out energy. This is due to an adherent sheath of matrix on the fibre surface which is not present at the lower strain rates.

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Microstructural characterisation of SF RTP's is highly complex, especially in a three-phase system. The combination of image analysis techniques for recording large numbers of fibres and a computer simulation and correction program to allow for the limitations of the analyser when dealing with a large fibre length range, can produce sensible results. Fortunately in this series of tests the fibres within the mouldings were mainly oriented within a single plane due to the mould surface constraints. Thus the moulded material could be modelled as being composed of plies of varying average orientation. The rubber was distributed uniformly throughout the specimens. The main effect of the rubber was to reduce the shear strength of the interface while at the same time to improve the fracture toughness and critical strain energy release rate of the matrix.

The fracture mechanics properties of coupled short glass fibre reinforced polypropylene toughened with rubber were highly strain rate dependent. At low strain rates the addition of glass fibres degrade the toughness of the material. The fibres act as discontinuities within the matrix, aiding initiation and propagation of a crack. At higher strain rates the fibres toughen the material by increasing the energy dissipation associated with fibre pull-out. These effects resulted in changes in the fracture surface morphology. Fibres pulled-out at low strain rates had clean surfaces. At higher strain rates the surface of pulled-out fibres was coated in an adherent sheath of matrix material. These effects are a direct consequence of the viscoelastic nature of the matrix. At low strain rates the matrix deforms plastically. At impact speeds the matrix responds in a predominately brittle manner.

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